

Tartarothyasira gen. nov., a replacement name for *Tartarothyas* Oliver & Chen, 2024

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Oliver and Chen (2024) introduced the genus name *Tartarothyas* for a species of hadal bivalve (Thyasiroidea: Thyasiridae) from the Japan Trench. It has now come to our attention that *Tartarothyas* was already introduced for a genus of water mites (Acari: Hydrachnidia: Hydryphantidae) by Viets in 1934 with the type species *T. micrommata* Viets, 1934. This renders *Tartarothyas* Oliver & Chen, 2024 a junior homonym of *Tartarothyas* Viets, 1934.

As a consequence, here we introduce the replacement genus name *Tartarothyasira* gen. nov. for *Tartarothyas* Oliver & Chen, 2024, with the type species *Tartarothyasira hadalis* (Okutani, Fujikura & Kojima, 1999).

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